

NEODC

- **NEODC is the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) designated data centre for Earth Observation**
- **Users can register, search the NEODC catalogue and request access to datasets on the web site www.neodc.rl.ac.uk**
- **We welcome email enquiries about EO data and provide support once data has been supplied. Contact neodc@rl.ac.uk**

Datasets

NEODC datasets are available for free download to registered users. Access restrictions apply to some data, contact NEODC for details.

- **ARSF data:**

NERC Airborne Research and Survey Facility data (ATM, CASI, LiDAR) since 1982

- **Aerial photography:**

High resolution aerial photographs from the NERC ARSF

- **NEXTMap Britain:**

High-resolution digital elevation data

- **ERS/Envisat data:**

MERIS, SCIAMACHY, MIPAS, (A)SAR

- **Commercial satellite datasets:**

LANDSAT, SPOT

MERIS MTCI, Europe, July 2007

- **MERIS MTCI:**

MERIS Terrestrial Chlorophyll Index; global and regional composites

- **AVHRR FASIR:**

FASIR adjusted NDVI and biological parameter fields

- **SHAC 2000:**

Data from the SHAC2000 Synthetic Aperture Radar and Hyperspectral Airborne Campaign

- **(A)ATSR Multimission Data:**

ATSR-1/ATSR-2/AATSR 16-year archive

AATSR Sea Surface Temperature, June 2006 (STFC/Defra/ESA/NERC)